

Table S1. Clinical characteristics of study patients

	Control (n=10)	Preeclampsia (n=10)	p-value
Maternal age (years)	36±1.6	34.2±1.6	NS
Gestational age (weeks)	37.9±0.2	34.9±0.5	P<0.001
Nulliparous	4	6	NS
Caesarean delivery before labor onset	10	10	NS
Systolic blood pressure at delivery (mmHg)	110±3	169±2	P<0.001
Diastolic blood pressure at delivery (mmHg)	64±2	101	P<0.001
Weight of neonate at birth (z-score)	0.2±0.2	-1.6±0.2	P<0.001
Placental weight (g)	561±40	379±21	P<0.001
Fetal growth restriction	0	5	P<0.001

Values are reported as mean ± standard error of the mean. NS, not significant.

Table S2.**Primer sets for PCR analysis for human**

Gene	primer sequences 5'-3'	sequence accession number
PTCH1 Fw	AGGGACTTCAGGATGCATTTGACAG	NM_001083605.1
PTCH1 Rv	CATCCACCAGACGCTGTTTAGTCA	
GLI2 Fw	GCTAACGAGGGATTACTTTGGCCAA	NM_005270.4
GLI2 Rv	TAGAGGAATTCAGGTGGACCAGGAA	
GCM1 Fw	ATCTACCTGAGACCTGCCATCT	NM_003643.3
GCM1 Rv	CACAGTTGGGACAGCGTTT	
ERVW-1 Fw	TGAACACTAGTCACTGGGTTCCATG	NM_001130925.1
ERVW-1 Rv	AATTGGGGCGTAGTAGAGGTTGTG	
CGB Fw	CCCACAACCCCGAGGTATAAAG	NM_000737.3
CGB Rv	ATGCTCAGCAGCAGCAACAG	
ADCY1 Fw	CTGCGAGGACGATGACAAG	NM_001281768.1
ADCY1 Rv	CAGGGTGGGAGACCAAAA	
ADCY2 Fw	CTGCTCGCCGTCTTCTTC	NM_020546.2
ADCY2 Rv	CAGGGCAGTTGGAAGTGTATT	
ADCY3 Fw	ACGGTGATGGTGTTCCTCAT	NM_001320613.1
ADCY3 Rv	AGTGTCCGTGCCAGTTTTTC	
ADCY4 Fw	ACCAGGACTGAGAATAGCCTTG	NM_001198592.1
ADCY4 Rv	CAGTCTGATGATGTTGGGAAGA	
ADCY5 Fw	CGACGTCTGGTCTAACGATG	NM_183357.2
ADCY5 Rv	TAGCCTTGGTGTGATGTGGATG	
ADCY6 Fw	CCTCCATTGCCAACTTCTCT	NM_015270.4
ADCY6 Rv	CGCTCCTCGCTGATAATCTC	
ADCY7 Fw	ATGGAGAACGTGAACCGCCTTC	NM_001114.4
ADCY7 Rv	GTTGACATCGCACTCTGTGTAGAAC	
ADCY8 Fw	TCAAGCCATTCTCACTGATGTT	NM_001115.2
ADCY8 Rv	TGAACACTTCATCCCTCATTTG	
ADCY9 Fw	CAGGACCAGCTATCAGGAAGA	NM_001116.3
ADCY9 Rv	TGGTCGACAGAAACACATCC	
ADCY10 Fw	AGGCCTAGACATCCGAGTCA	NM_018417.5
ADCY10 Rv	CATCTCCAAAGACCAACATGC	
IGF1 Fw	TGTGGAGACAGGGGCTTTTA	NM_001111283.2
IGF1 Rv	ATCCACGATGCCTGTCTGA	
IGF2 Fw	CCCCTCCGACCGTGCT	NM_000612.5
IGF2 Rv	TCATATTGGAAGAACTTGCCCA	
IGF1R Fw	TTCAGCGCTGCTGATGTG	NM_000875.4
IGF1R Rv	AAGTTCCCGGCTCATGGT	
IRS1 Fw	TATGCCAGCATCAGTTTCCA	NM_005544.2
IRS1 Rv	TTTGCTGAGGTCATTTAGGTCTT	
GAPDH Fw	GAGTCAACGGATTTGGTCGTATTGG	NM_002046.5
GAPDH Rv	GCCATGGGTGGAATCATATTGGAAC	

Primer sets for PCR analysis for mouse

Gene	primer sequences 5'-3'	sequence accession number
PTCH1 Fw	TGACAAAGCCGACTACATGC	NM_001083605.1
PTCH1 Rv	GTACTIONGATGGGCTCTGCTG	
GLI2 Fw	GCAGACTGCACCAAGGAGTA	NM_005270.4
GLI2 Rv	CGTGGATGTGTTTATTGTTGA	
IGF1 Fw	AGCAGCCTTCCAACCTCAATTAT	NM_010512.5
IGF1 Rv	TGAAGACGACATGATGTGTATCTTTAT	
IGF2 Fw	CGCTTCAGTTTGTCTGTTTCG	NM_010514.3
IGF2 Rv	GCAGCACTCTTCCACGATG	
IGF1R Fw	GAGAATTTCTTCCACAATTCCATC	NM_010513.2
IGF1R Rv	CACTTGACATGACGTCTCTCC	
IRS1 Fw	CTATGCCAGCATCAGCTTCC	NM_010570.4
IRS1 Rv	TTGCTGAGGTCATTTAGGTCTTC	
GAPDH Fw	GGGTTCTATAAATACGGACTGC	NM_008084.3
GAPDH Rv	CCATTTTGTCTACGGGACGA	

Table S3. Primer sets for bisulfite PCR analysis

Region	primer sequences 5'-3'
Region 1 Fw	GGTTGGTTTTGAATTTTTGATTTTA
Region 1 Rv	CTAAACCCTCAAACCACACCAC
Region 2 Fw	TGTATGTGTGTGGTTGTGTATATGG
Region 2 Rv	CATCATCACTTTCTTTACAAATCCT
Region 3 Fw	ATTTGGGTAAAAGATGATGAGAATG
Region 3 Rv	ACACCCCTACTACCTCCAATA
Region 1 Fw for nested PCR	TTTTTAAGGGGTTTGAGAGATTT
Region 1 Rv for nested PCR	TCCTCATTAATTTTCTAACCAAAA

Table S4. Candidate pathways potentially relevant to SHH pathway

	GSE10588	GSE25906
BIOCARTA_CFTR_PATHWAY	R=0.59, P<0.001	R=0.69, P<0.001
BIOCARTA_DREAM_PATHWAY	R=0.54, P<0.001	R=0.68, P<0.001
BIOCARTA_CARM1_PATHWAY	R=0.68, P<0.001	R=0.68, P<0.001
BIOCARTA_AKAPCENTROSOME_PATHWAY	R=0.61, P<0.001	R=0.63, P<0.001
REACTOME_PKA_MEDIATED_PHOSPHORYLATION_OF_CREB	R=0.58, P<0.001	R=0.62, P<0.001
BIOCARTA_AGPCR_PATHWAY	R=0.57, P<0.001	R=0.57, P<0.001
REACTOME_HORMONE_SENSITIVE_LIPASE_HSL_MEDIATED_TRIACYLGLYCEROL_HYDROLYSIS	R=0.75, P<0.001	R=0.51, P<0.001
BIOCARTA_IGF1R_PATHWAY	R=0.55, P<0.001	R=0.45, P<0.001
MIPS_KCNQ1_MACROMOLECULAR_COMPLEX	R=0.60, P<0.001	R=0.45, P<0.001

Fig. S1**Figure S1. Sonic hedgehog pathway score**

(Left) Activation scores of the sonic hedgehog pathway were significantly correlated with the expression level of *PTCH1* in the placentas (GSE10588), indicating that *PTCH1* is a surrogate marker for the sonic hedgehog pathway. The scores were normalized to the range 0-1. (Right) The placental sonic hedgehog pathway scores were independent of gestational age (GSE75010). NS, not significant.

Fig. S2

Figure S2. IGF axis in placenta

(A) Expressions of major components of the IGF axis in the control (n=10) and preeclampsia (n=10) placentas. (B, C) Correlation between placental expressions of the IGF axis and birth weight z-scores and placental weights in the control and preeclampsia pregnancies (n=10 in each group). (D) IGF1R pathway score and major components of the IGF axis. The expressions of major components of the IGF axis, *IGF1R* (left) and *IRS1* (right), were significantly correlated with the IGF1R pathway scores, implying that both *IGF1R* and *IRS1* expressions are representative of the IGF1R pathway. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.